

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

WYRED Slogan Competition Call For
Participation
English Version
WP4_D4.2.2

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1 Introduction

A central aim of the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) is to give children and young people a voice, particularly in relation to research into issues that concern them, and how its results are discussed and presented.

Related to the proposed activities, it is mandatory building the WYRED network by reaching out to potential participants and engaging them through a set of preliminary activities. One of these activities is to have a slogan. To do that, a slogan competition has been set up to engage young people with the project. This deliverable means the call for participation that the WYRED consortium has developed and published in the website.

2 Slogan competition call for participation

Do you wonder about how **contemporary society** works?

Would you like to *improve* the reality we live in?

Do you feel that **YOUNG PEOPLE ARE NOT REPRESENTED** in media or politics?

Would you like your opinion to **be heard**?

Are you curious about the role **digital media** plays in self-expression and participation in society?

Welcome to the WYRED project!

WHAT IS WYRED?

a framework in which YOU can express YOUR perspectives and interests

a space where you can explore and enrich YOUR perspectives

a channel through which YOU can communicate YOUR perspectives

HOW DO WE DO THIS?

1. we get together, and we *discuss* the issues that matter to you

online, offline, digital, virtual, real

2. we *choose the questions* we want to explore

**privacy, migration, identity, trust, relationships, work, safety, climate change, inequality,
gender, new technologies, globalisation, gaming, health,**

3. we decide together *how we want to explore* them

video, journalism, surveys, citizen science, photography, interviews, data analysis, observation

4. then we work on our *projects*

local, international, individual, groups, short, long

5. and *present our results* to policymakers and society

Join us!

GET WYRED!

Use your creativity!

propose a SLOGAN For **WYRED!**

SLOGAN: a **short striking** or **memorable** phrase used to get people's attention. Used in advertising, and other contexts!

Get involved!

Eligible proposals can be a text slogan or an image or video with text expressing your perceptions about young people in digital society, in English. You can participate individually or as a group.

By submitting a proposal, you agree to allow the use of the slogan in the framework of the WYRED project & related activities.

Who can participate?

Anyone aged 8 to 30 years old who is willing to be part of the European atmosphere and participate in the spread of young people's point of view on online and offline life!

How to participate?

EASY! Click on the link <https://goo.gl/forms/jh64i3LjXqWextP2> and fill in the form (takes 1 minute!) If you want to propose an image or a video you can send it by email to

info@wyredproject.eu

DEADLINE 29/03/2017

How will we use your slogan?

We will use the slogan on the website <https://wyredproject.eu/> on our social media channels (Instagram, Facebook, etc.) and in our communications and events (national and international)

The winning slogans, according to age groups (under 14, 14-17, and over 17) will be published on the homepage of WYRED <https://wyredproject.eu/#home>. The prizes will be 30€ book vouchers.

invite your friends to join IN!

3 References

- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2016). The WYRED Project: A Technological Platform for a Generative Research and Dialogue about Youth Perspectives and Interests in Digital Society. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 9(4), vi-x.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Kearney, N. A. (2016). Networked youth research for empowerment in digital society. The WYRED project. In F. J. García-Peñalvo (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (TEEM'16) (Salamanca, Spain, November 2-4, 2016)* (pp. 3-9). New York, NY, USA: ACM.